
Use of Financial Statements in auditing the Performance of an Organization - A Survey Based Study in Jordan Banking Sector

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Abstract

This research aims to identify the use of financial statements in auditing the performance of the organization. This study evaluates the multiple aspects of the business for the company that is operating in Jordan. In relation to the aim of the study, the researcher has selected Jordanian Banking Sector for analysis and collect related data of the Jordanian Banking Sector. The focus of this research is based on analysis of different elements that is applied in business practices of the company for judging business performance. The data of this research is collected through a close ended questionnaire to identify the importance of financial statements in evaluating performance of Jordanian Banking Sector. This study is supported by data that is obtained from survey of Jordanian Banking Sector operated in Jordan along with secondary and primary data. In addition to this, the finding of this research specified different methods for financial analysis that is applied by companies. The implemented method of this research is descriptive that identify different use of the financial statement in the business. In relation to this, the finding of the study specified that financial statement of the company is not only limited to providing information of quantitative data as it contains different qualitative aspects that support for auditing organizational performance as well as support for making effective business decisions.

Keywords: *Financial Statements, Organizational Performance, Banking Sector, Jordan.*

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper aims to evaluate the use of financial statements for judging business performance that is operating in the region of Jordan. For evaluating the performance of a company, managers and financial analysts require information about company operations and management. Jordan [1] identified that evaluation of organizational performance measurement systems is critical to evaluate as it is influenced by multiple elements of the business. However, the most important tool for performance evaluation is an analysis of financial statements. To attain the aim of the study, this research analyses performance of Jordanian Banking Sector through financial statement analysis. It has been found that inappropriate measure of organizational performance evaluation may result in severe consequences [2]. Each factor is considered in performance measurement process need to have a contribution to attaining business success.

In addition, managers and analysts use a series of the financial statement for auditing organization performance to deal with different elements. However, the methods that consider financial aspects, respecting the characteristics of the company analyzed, tend to have greater importance. Another important aspect of that is included in this research is that the Jordanian Banking Sector is divided into several groups. Similarly, there are several stakeholders through that companies operations are

affected by their performance. This includes suppliers, creditors, government, customers and the community at large [3]. In this context, De Jonghe and Öztekin [4] pointed out that each of these stakeholders has a set of specific objectives, goals, and expectations that evaluates the performance and directly contributed for attaining the success.

Background of the Study

The process of measuring organizational performance includes all aspects of management that remain permanent and incurred in repetitive process, where measurements of the performance are depended on different activities. In relation to this, financial elements of the business play an important role in monitoring the company's progress and to correct any inaccuracies of operational business performance. In addition, the manager goes through organizational performance evaluation based on company capabilities to respond to environmental changes, changing in nature of competition and creation of value for the customer. In relation to this, Jordanian Banking Sector is operating as the leading sector with its control over several subsidiaries [5]. In this context, the financial services of Jordanian Banking Sector are widely spread that include consumers, corporations, and other financial institutions. The main products of the Jordanian Banking Sector include consumer banking, corporate, treasury services and institutional banking services. Furthermore, the banks have developed a widespread network in the key financial market of the world that includes locations such as London, Singapore, Dubai, Paris, Sydney, Frankfurt, and Bahrain. In addition, there are multiple companies, subsidiaries and affiliates companies of Jordanian Banking Sector operating at different locations. With this widespread of financial service based business use of financial statement is prominent for auditing business performance of Jordanian Banking Sector.

Problem of the Study

The financial statements of the company show the past, the accounting implementation in it has a limiting factor for its use [6]. There are several indexes that can be used to evaluate the performance of a company, but each of these will have its importance depending on the evaluation of business performance. In an organization, it is important to use a quantitative tool that in some way helps the analyst to work with the set of indexes chosen by management in auditing organizational performance.

However, implementation of several techniques may transpose the impact of financial performance [7]. Therefore, this tool can be used by management of Jordanian Banking Sector for identifying their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. In addition, through this external public that has interest in the company support managerial decisions that take into account the financial performance.

Research Questions

Based on the above discussion, the research study is conducted for identifying answers to the following questions:

1. What is the importance of financial statements in the Jordanian Banking Sector?
2. What is the role of the financial statement for auditing performance of Jordanian Banking Sector?
3. What are the different methods for evaluating business performance through financial statements?

Objectives of the Research

The study aims to identify the uses of the financial statement for auditing performance of the company. For attaining the aim of the study, this research achieves the following objectives:

1. To recognize the importance of financial statements in the company.
2. To determine the role of the financial statement for auditing performance of Jordanian Banking Sector.
3. To identify a different method for evaluating business performance through financial statements.

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The discussion of the financial statements of the companies is mainly done through the indexes that give insight into the organizational performance, health, and support for its survival over time [8]. Use of financial statement is one of the main tools used to measure the efficiency of the company in the use of its resources and its opportunities to maximize overall benefits. The reason for this evaluation has provided several benefits to financial analyst, managers, and investors of Jordanian Banking Sector. Meanwhile, it is easy to hear that Jordanian Banking Sector requires to increase their market share, maximize revenue, create a new policy for dividend distribution, maximizing return on capital or profit generation capacity of the business. It has been

recognized that all organizational goals of the business for performance have the potential to audit their performance through financial indicators. According to Vishny and Zingales [9], that analysis of financial statements provides an instant snapshot of economic/financial aspects of companies.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The business performance analysis is presented in the form of a report that includes an analysis of its structure, the level of equity and a set of indices and indicators that are carefully evaluated by which the analyst's conclusion is formed [10]. In contrast to this, García-Morales, Jiménez-Barrionuevo [11] specified that the analysis of financial information is focused inside and outside of business that is not limited to the calculation of mere performance indicators. In the preparation of the Balance Sheets and other Financial Statements, which in Jordan are called as Financial Statements. This includes some procedures are required by regulatory authorities. This analysis includes evaluation of Jordan accounting standards, Jordan Corporate Law, Income Tax Regulations. Moreover, Jordanian Banking Sector also considers standards that are issued by the Central Bank of Jordan and the Securities and Exchange Commission. In addition to this, Aizenman, Binici [12] pointed out that from the evaluation of financial statements, the analyst arrives at a more precise conclusion, and needs to know regarding business procedures recommended by the standards in force. It has been observed that one of these requirements of regulatory authorities includes being financial, tariff, tax and operational assessment of business performance [13].

Evaluation of the organizational performance of the company is the main business aspect in which financial statement is evaluated that aims to highlight a certain aspect of the company's situation. In addition to this, Fracassi [8] indicated that there are numerous elements of financial statement that determine comparison patterns for the business. In addition to this financial statement is the most common elements that treat the accounting-financial analysis as a system of information that transforms data obtain mainly from the financial statements into useful information for the decision-making process that affect internal and external elements of the company. Therefore, business efficiency could be evaluated on the basis of quality, extent, and adequacy of information. Petty, Titman [14] pointed out that financial statement analysis is an art of

knowing how to extract useful objectives for the purposes of the traditional financial system and financial reporting and its extensions and details that are required for judging business performance. In this regard, Brigham and Ehrhardt [15] stress that each financial analyst needs to choose his or her own set of relations to make a particular analysis of business performance to arrive at different conclusions regarding the same business practices organization.

In relation to use of financial statement for evaluating organizational performance of the company, the key performance indicators that are identified from financial statement analysis is covered in the following figure:

Figure 1: Types of Financial Indicators
(Source: kpi-examples.blogspot.com)

The financial statement of the business is considered as one of the main tools to aid decision making and can be divided into several aspects [16]. According to Marshall [17] accounting analysis has objectives to analyze reports and statements with the purpose of providing numerical information preferably of two or more periods to implement the administrators and shareholders strategy for strengthening the business position. In addition to this, Williams [18] specified that financial statement in the company is developed that support different forms of decision for judging business performance. In this regard, the analysis of financial statement is made in several business forms that contain financial statement analysis, identification of financial leverage and economic analysis [19]. In this context, financial analysis is traditionally carried out through indicators for global analysis. Additionally, this is used for analyzing the short, medium and long-term rate funds and turnover of the business key accounts such as total assets turnover. Moreover, financial evaluation includes

identification of debt level in proportion to equity, which is used to measure the degree that is applied for third-party capital and its effects on the formation of the rate of return on equity. In contrast to this, financial evaluation can be also made through economic analysis that measured profitability, return on equity, net earnings per share and return on operating investments in business [20].

It has been identified from the study of Hoskin, Fizzell [21] that the true analysis of Financial Statements needs to cover the key areas along with important financial elements. This contains evaluation of Assets (Current, Long-Term and Permanent) and Liabilities (Current and Long-Term Liabilities) using the principles and other rules contained in the international financial reporting standards. Moreover, Bebbington, Unerman [22] indicated that the analysis of revenues and expenses are mainly associated with the determination of documentary frauds with the intention of manipulation of overall business results. In this context, Williams [18] identified that financial statement analysis supports the business to recognize weak business areas that can be supported through appropriate management strategy. On the other hand, verification and determination of administrative or judicial actions are imperative elements that include both active and passive financial account, concerning labor, social security, income and tax. In relation to this, the most important element of the business is the risk and minimum capital assessment that is required by banks. According to Resolution of Basel Agreement, which includes limits of indebtedness, risk, minimum capital, fixed assets and certain types of operations that needs to be carried out in the banking sector.

Faced with server impact of external environmental factors that result in uncertainty where many organization is subject to management techniques and financial tools becomes essential for the success of the business. In this context, it has been observed entrepreneurs who choose to open their business, but do not possess the knowledge necessary for good management, due to lack of importance given to performance indicators [20]. Most of the organizations have their growth cycle interrupted which include several factors, among them the most highlighted element is the good financial management that plays an important role during the decision-making process which will result in either possible success or failure [17]. Therefore, it is notable that this performance has a major impact on

organizations. In relation to this, there are many factors through which financial management influence organizations that include the use of performance indicators or identifying the differences between business tools that are applied in an organization.

According to Lefebvre, Simonova [23], the world is in constant evolution; organizations have to need to be prepared to face the numerous transitions. Currently, access to all information has become faster, that includes the way information is used a competitive differential. In relation to this, the crisis scenario results in limited access to several business opportunities. However, it is precisely at this point that organizations need several opportunities that are visible to specific business segments only. In addition, the business requires to understand the importance of changing and correcting failures to achieve better results of organizational performance. In relation to this, most of the financial information is linked to the financial area as Cooper, Ezzamel [24] specified the importance of financial analysis as a tool for recognizing final results and states that financial statements of the company is the language of business and accounting are included communication channels that provide management with data and information to diagnose the performance and financial health of the company. In this context, the areas of finance are concerned with capturing and optimally allocating resources from the operational activities of the business.

4. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the importance of financial statement for evaluating the overall performance of the company. In relation to this, a different aspect of financial statement analysis is evaluated and analyzed. The method of this study is survey based descriptive approach through which survey is conducted from employees of Jordanian Banking Sector to identify implementation of the financial statement for measuring overall business performance. The source of data in this study includes both primary and secondary sources that are used in this study. In this research, the applied research approach is descriptive that evaluates the importance of financial statement for auditing organizational performance of Jordanian Banking Sector [25]. Primary data of the research is obtained through a survey that is based on employees of Jordanian Banking Sector. The sampling strategy is based on convenience, and sample participants

include around 150 individuals from a managerial position of Jordanian Banking Sector. In addition to this, collected data of this research is analyzed through a quantitative approach by using SPSS. Data analysis of the research enables the researcher to obtain accurate and valid results that support for identification of financial trends of Jordanian Banking Sector and its importance for judging business performance.

The following are the hypothesis of this study

H0: Financial Statements does not have significant impact on Performance Evaluation

H1: Financial Statements have significant impact on Performance Evaluation

H0: Financial Statements does not significantly assist the banking sector of Jordan to perform effective audit

H2: Financial Statements significantly assist the banking sector of Jordan to perform effective audit

5. RESULTS

With consideration of the research purpose, the survey questionnaire has been developed to obtain information from the employees of Jordanian Banking Sector to identifying the use of financial statement for auditing overall business performance. The first section of the survey questionnaire is demographics which include participants' age, gender and position at the Jordanian Banking Sector.

Table 1: Gender

Gender			
	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	83	55	55
Female	67	45	100
Total	150	100	

From the conversion of research data in quantitative terms, it has been identified that more participants of this study are male while only 45% female participant take part in this survey.

Table 2: Age Group

Age			
	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-30 years	15	10	10
30-40 years	39	26	36
40-50 years	22	15	51
50-60 years	74	49	100
Total	150	100	

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-30 years	15	10	10
30-40 years	39	26	36
40-50 years	22	15	51
50-60 years	74	49	100
Total	150	100	

The survey of this research is based on identification of responses from the senior managerial level. Similarly, there were very few participants with less experience in the Jordanian Banking Sector. The frequency of this study reveals that most of the participants of the study were above 30 years old. In addition, 50% of participants were between the ages of 50 to 60 years.

Table 3: Position in Organization

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Executives	45	30.0	30.0
Managerial	60	40.0	70.0
Operational	45	30.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	

This study evaluates the use of financial statement for auditing organizational performance of the company. Therefore all respondents were taken from different levels of management in Jordanian Banking Sector. However, the higher participants of the study are employee from managerial position.

Table 4:

Performance evaluation is an integral part of the organization.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	7	4.7	4.7
Disagree	16	10.7	15.3

Neither Agree Nor Disagree	42	28	43.3
Agree	46	30.7	74
Strongly Agree	39	26	100
Total	150	100	

Evaluation of business performance is made in the business continuously to identify key strength and overcome any weaknesses in performance. In this regard, 4.7% of the respondents were strongly disagree, 10% were disagree and neutral. On the contrary, 30% of the participants were agree and 26% were strongly agree

Table 5:

Auditing performance is based on multiple business elements.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	5	3.3	3.3
Disagree	24	16.0	19.3
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	46	30.7	50.0
Agree	52	34.7	84.7
Strongly Agree	23	15.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	

It is the fact that performance of the business is not based on one element as it develops through combination of different resources. For instance, the business cannot grow only with high investment as it requires human capital for proper allocation of resources in different activities. In this context, the response is in the view that organizational performance is based on different elements. However, financial information provides quality of information.

For the evaluation of business performance, financial statement is widely evaluated by different stakeholders. In response to this, the participants were agree with accuracy of financial information for evaluating business performance.

Table 6:

Financial statement provides useful information regarding business performance.
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	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	22	14.7	17.3
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	46	30.7	48
Agree	50	33.3	81.3
Strongly Agree	28	18.7	100
Total	150	100	

Table 7:

Financial information lack quality of information.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	7	4.7	4.7
Disagree	20	13.3	18
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	44	29.3	47.3
Agree	50	33.3	80.7
Strongly Agree	29	19.3	100
Total	150	100	

It has been identified from the discussion of literature that certain researcher is in the view that financial information cannot be converted in qualitative data. Through this question it has been identified that financial information lacks quality of information as most of the research participants favors this statement.

Table 8:

Use of financial is an important business activity.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	4	4
Disagree	21	14	18
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	46	30.7	48.7
Agree	49	32.7	81.3
Strongly Agree	28	18.7	100
Total	150	100	

It is not possible to consider the existence of any business without financial resources. The answer on

the importance of financial for the business activity includes combination of responses. However, the same principle is accepted by most of the participants which indicated the importance of financial statements for business activities.

Table 9:

Through the application of different analytical tools financial statement support for auditing business performance.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	8	5.3	5.3
Disagree	17	11.3	16.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	44	29.3	46
Agree	44	29.3	75.3
Strongly Agree	37	24.7	100
Total	150	100	

The importance of financial statements for evaluating business performance cannot be denied. However, the finding of this study specified that organizational performance of the business can be evaluated effectively through evaluation of financial statements of the company.

Table 10:

Ratio analysis is the effective method to obtain the quality of information for organizational performance.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	25	16.7	19.3
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	39	26	45.3
Agree	61	40.7	86
Strongly Agree	21	14	100
Total	150	100	

One of the most common methods for evaluating financial statements of the company is to conduct ratio analysis. In response to this around 50% of employees agree with the statement while 20 percent neither agreed nor disagree. In addition, 30 percent of

participants do not consider ratio analysis as an important measure for evaluating business performance.

Table 11:

Cash flow analysis support for identifying potential risk factors.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	3	2	2
Disagree	15	10	12
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	44	29.3	41.3
Agree	62	41.3	82.7
Strongly Agree	26	17.3	100
Total	150	100	

The most common interest of the Bank is to identify cash flow that is available for operational activities in business. However, this is considered as an important element for identifying risk factors. The finding of this study specified that 40% and 20% of the research participants were strongly agree and agree that cash flow identify potential risk factors in business.

Table 12:

Evaluation of financial statement provides the basis for making a business decision.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	18	12	14.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	40	26.7	41.3
Agree	59	39.3	80.7
Strongly Agree	29	19.3	100
Total	150	100	

From the responses of research participants it has been identified that financial information of the business has supported for making effective business decision. The result in this regard specified that 65 percent were strongly agree and agree with this. On the other hand only 35 percent were disagree.

Table 13:

Financial information is limited to quantitative business data.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	5	3.3	3.3
Disagree	20	13.3	16.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	33	22	38.7
Agree	60	40	78.7
Strongly Agree	32	21.3	100
Total	150	100	

In response the limitation of financial information on quantitative data it has been identified that most of the employees were agree and strongly agree with this statement. This indicated that employee perceive financial statement as the source of quantitative data rather than qualitative data.

Table 14:

Financial statement allow the firm to show financial strengths to stakeholders			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	2	1.3	1.3
Disagree	17	11.3	12.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	47	31.3	44
Agree	62	41.3	85.3
Strongly Agree	22	14.7	100
Total	150	100	

In the above question, the respondents were asked the above mentioned question. It was found from the results, that majority of respondents were in favor of the idea that financial statement allow the firm to show financial strengths to stakeholders. It also indicated that the financial statement has vital importance for the organisation in terms of showing financial strength.

Table 15:

With the help of financial statement, the firm can take credit by showing its financial performance.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	18	12	14.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	41	27.3	42
Agree	62	41.3	83.3
Strongly Agree	25	16.7	100
Total	150	100	

Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	18	12	14.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	41	27.3	42
Agree	62	41.3	83.3
Strongly Agree	25	16.7	100
Total	150	100	

In the aforementioned question, the respondents were asked about financial statements and its usefulness in terms of taking credit. It was found from the results, that majority of respondents were in favor of the idea that the firm can take credit by showing its financial performance with the help of financial statement.

Table 16:

Financial statement helps the banking sector to perform timely financial audit.			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	21	14	16.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	37	24.7	41.3
Agree	59	39.3	80.7
Strongly Agree	29	19.3	100
Total	150	100	

In the aforementioned question, the respondents were asked about financial statements and its effectiveness to conduct timely audit. It was found from the results, that majority of respondents were in favor of the statement that financial statement helps the banking sector to perform timely financial audit.

Table 17:

Financial statements have a vital role in auditing of banking sector			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	18	12	14.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	41	27.3	42
Agree	62	41.3	83.3
Strongly Agree	25	16.7	100
Total	150	100	

Strongly Disagree	3	2	2
Disagree	17	11.3	13.3
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	45	30	43.3
Agree	49	32.7	76
Strongly Agree	36	24	100
Total	150	100	

In the above question, the respondents were asked about importance of financial statements in auditing. It was found from the results, that majority of respondents were in favor of the statement that financial statement helps the banking sector to perform financial analysis as well as business assessment.

Table 18:

Financial statements help auditors to quickly assess abnormalities in the financial position			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	2	1.3	1.3
Disagree	25	16.7	18
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	50	33.3	51.3
Agree	51	34	85.3
Strongly Agree	22	14.7	100
Total	150	100	

In the question mentioned above, respondents were asked about the role of financial statement and the way it helps auditors to trace abnormalities in the financial performance. Results showed that majority of respondents were in favor of the statement that financial statements help auditors to quickly assess abnormalities in the financial position thus resulting in effective audit.

Table 19:

Financial statements allow the auditor to assess the reasons for abnormal changes in the financial position			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	3	2	2
Disagree	23	15.3	17.3

Neither Agree Nor Disagree	46	30.7	48
Agree	52	34.7	82.7
Strongly Agree	26	17.3	100
Total	150	100	

In the question mentioned above, respondents were asked about the role of financial statement in the assessment of abnormal changes in the financial position of banking sector. Results showed that most of participants were in favor of the idea Financial statements allow the auditor to assess the reasons for abnormal changes in the financial position.

Table 20:

Financial statements show the possible threats and chances of fraud			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	4	4
Disagree	20	13.3	17.3
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	44	29.3	46.7
Agree	52	34.7	81.3
Strongly Agree	28	18.7	100
Total	150	100	

In the question mentioned above, it was asked from respondents that whether financial statements show threats of frauds or not. Results identified that most of participants were in favor of the idea that financial statements show the possible threats and chances of fraud therefore, it can be estimated that financial statements are vital in order to trace frauds.

Table 21:

Financial statement analysis help the auditor to rectify errors and improve accuracy of financial reporting			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	2.7	2.7
Disagree	21	14	16.7
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	47	31.3	48
Agree	48	32	80
Strongly Agree	30	20	100

Total	150	100	
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In the above mentioned question, it was asked from respondents that whether financial statements helps the auditor to rectify errors and improve accuracy or not. Results identified that most of participants were in favor of the statement that financial statement analysis help the auditor to rectify errors and improve accuracy of financial reporting.

Table 22:

With proper evaluation of financial statement, banking sector can perform effective and efficient audit			
	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	4	4
Disagree	17	11.3	15.3
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	52	34.7	50
Agree	44	29.3	79.3
Strongly Agree	31	20.7	100
Total	150	100	

In the question mentioned above, it was asked from respondents that financial statements helps the banking sector of Jordan to perform effective and efficient audit or not. Results showed that most of participants were in favor of the statement that with proper evaluation of financial statement, banking sector can perform effective and efficient audit.

Table 23:

Financial statements increases the accuracy and effectiveness of audit through revelation of financial performance.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	2	1.3	1.3
Disagree	25	16.7	18
Neither Agree Nor Disagree	43	28.7	46.7
Agree	60	40	86.7
Strongly Agree	20	13.3	100

Total	150	100	
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In the question mentioned above, it was asked from respondents that financial statements financial statements increase the accuracy of firm through identification of business performance or not. Results showed that most of participants were in favor of the statement that financial statements increases the accuracy and effectiveness of audit through revelation of financial performance.

In order to assess the difference between means of auditing performance, financial statements and business performance, the researcher used one sample t-test. In other words, the aim of the test was to test whether the purpose of financial statement and auditing performance is different towards business performance or not.

Table 24: T-Test

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Auditing Performance	150	3.54	.513	.042
Financial Statements	150	3.54	.513	.042
Business Performance	150	3.49	.528	.043

From the aforementioned table, it is identified that there were 150 observations in the test because of the sample size which was 150. In addition, the mean of auditing performance and financial statement was 3.54 while the mean of business performance was 3.49.

Table 25: T-Test

	One-Sample Test					
	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Auditing Performance	84.463	149	.000	3.540	3.46	3.62

Financial Statements	84.463	149	.000	3.540	3.46	3.62
Business Performance	81.075	149	.000	3.493	3.41	3.58

The aforementioned table shows the results of the one sample t-test. It was found from the results that the null hypothesis of all variables have been rejected because the p-value of all variables is less than 0.05. However, the null hypothesis of the test was that the mean of the variable is same across the population. But this hypothesis is rejected because of the p-value which concluded that mean of all variable is different across population. Finally, it can be summarized that the purpose of all variable is different in business of banking sector of Jordan. Furthermore, to assess the impact of financial statements and audit performance, the researcher applied regression analysis and found the following results.

Table 26: Model Summary

Model Summary^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin - Watson
1	.637 ^a	.405	.397	.410	2.195

a. Predictors: (Constant), Financial Statements, Auditing Performance
 b. Dependent Variable: Business Performance

It can be seen from the aforementioned table that the R was 63.7% which showed that the overall relation of all variables was around 63.7%. R-Square was around 40.5% which showed that the overall impact was 40.5% but the researcher did not considered it because the model was multivariate and therefore, adjusted r-square was of more importance. The adjusted r-square was 39.7% which showed that around 40% of combined impact of all independent variables towards dependent variable.

Table 27: ANOVA

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	16.817	2	8.409	50.092	.000 ^b
Residual	24.676	147	.168		
Total	41.493	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Business Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Financial Statements, Auditing Performance

The above table showed the most crucial factor of the regression analysis and that was statistical significance of the model. It was found from the above table that the model was significant because the p-value of the model was less than 0.05 which showed that the null hypothesis of the test was rejected. The H0 was that the model is insignificant or the regression is due to chance.

Table 28: Coefficients

Coefficients^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	.856	.266		3.223	.002
Auditing Performance	.400	.078	.389	5.145	.000
Financial Statements	.345	.078	.335	4.431	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Business Performance

The table mentioned above was the last table, which showed the coefficients of the model and their autocorrelation. It was found that the all variables were statistically significant because their p-value was less than 0.05. However, the constant of the model was 0.85 which showed that regardless of every variable, business performance will remain 0.85. The coefficient of financial statements and audit performance were 0.389 and 0.385 respectively

which showed that both variables have positive impact on business performance by around 38.9% and 38.5%. Finally, Tolerance and VIF statistics were used for checking multicollinearity of the model and it was found that there was no multicollinearity in the model because tolerance value was higher than 0.3 while the value of VIF was less than 10. It can be concluded from the regression analysis that audit performance and financial statements have a positive significant impact on business performance.

6. DISCUSSION

From the finding of the different research, it has been identified that financial statement analysis is based on three steps that include evaluation of reports, making adjustments in collected data and analyses the financial statements through ratio analysis [6]. In relation to this, the literature indicated financial statement use is an important element for auditing business performance [4]. This is confirm in from the finding of the study that financial statements provide quality of information. It has been found from the quantitative research that financial information of the business plays a key role in the business movement since financial institution performs the function using resources to generate earnings. Additionally, the organizational performance of financial institution based different business element. In addition to this Williams [18] indicated that whenever difference occurs in financial information and organizational performance the gap has been developed which emphasize business to apply specific analysis to fill the gap of the financial and organizational performance of the company.

The finding of the study suggest that financial statements is use for auditing business performance. It has been identified from the literature that financial management of Jordanian Banking Sector has applied quantitative measures for judging organizational performance. The finding of the research specified that use of financial information make a major contribution to the financial analysis and it is undeniable that the financial analysis involves not only quantitative variables but also contain in-depth details of qualitative variables [8]. In relation to this, Hoskin, Fizzell [21] is in the view that the use of quantitative tools into the process of evaluating organization performance based on the techniques of prioritizing. Similarly, findings of the study confirms that financial statement analysis of the company is an important element for evaluating business performance over including qualitative aspects of the

company [17]. Based on the finding of the study which specified that main concern of the company is to recognize the level of cash flows in business operations that is available for operational activities[23]. Therefore, it can be said that use of financial information for judging the business performance of the company play a vital role.

7. CONCLUSION

From the overall discussion, it has been concluded that use of financial plays an important role in auditing organizational performance of the bank. It has been found that the main important element of financial statement analysis is ratio analysis. In addition to this, the finding of the study specified that financial statement is not only limited to provide quantitative information about the company but also evaluates qualitative business aspects. In addition to this, the most important elements that identified the level of cash flows of the business which is required for operational activities of the company. In summarizing, the use of financial statements is mostly applied by companies that are operating in Jordan for evaluating organizational performance.

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9. APPENDIX

Survey Questionnaire

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>1. Gender</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male • Female <p>2. Age</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18-30 years • 30-40 years | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 40-50 years • 50-60 years <p>3. Position in organization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executives • Managerial • Operational |
|--|---|

No.	Question	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
H1: Financial Statements have significant impact on Performance Evaluation						
1.	Performance evaluation is an integral part of the organization.					
2.	Auditing performance is based on multiple business elements.					
3.	Financial statement provides useful information regarding business performance.					
4.	Financial information is limited to quantitative business data.					
5.	Financial information lack quality of information.					
6.	Use of financial is an important business activity.					
7.	Through the application of different analytical tools financial statement support for auditing business performance.					
8.	Ratio analysis is the effective method to obtain the quality of information for organizational performance.					
9.	Cash flow analysis support for identifying potential risk factors.					
10.	Evaluation of financial statement provides the basis for making a business decision.					
H2: Financial Statements significantly assist the banking sector of Jordan to perform effective audit						
1	Financial statement allow the firm to show financial strengths to stakeholders					
2	With the help of financial statement, the firm can take credit by showing its financial performance.					
3	Financial statement helps the banking sector to perform timely financial audit.					
4	Financial statements have a vital role in auditing of banking sector					

5	Financial statements help auditors to quickly assess abnormalities in the financial position					
6	Financial statements allow the auditor to assess the reasons for abnormal changes in the financial position					
7	Financial statements show the possible threats and chances of fraud					
8	Financial statement analysis help the auditor to rectify errors and improve accuracy of financial reporting					
9	With proper evaluation of financial statement, banking sector can perform effective and efficient audit					
10	Financial statements increases the accuracy and effectiveness of audit through revelation of financial performance.					

